

Replication Codebook V3

Climate Finance and Fiscal Capacity in SSA

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Overview

This document contains all Python code to replicate the V3 manuscript. Key changes from V2: (1) Resilience index no longer includes fiscal-governance capacity (circularity fix); (2) GFCF renamed to “public investment intensity”; (3) All analyses recalculated.

Requirements

pandas, numpy, statsmodels, linearmodels, scipy

Data

Input: climate_finance_v3_data_2002_2023.xlsx

1 Data Loading and Setup

```
1 import pandas as pd
2 import numpy as np
3 import statsmodels.api as sm
4 from linearmodels.panel import PanelOLS
5 from scipy.stats.mstats import winsorize
6 import warnings
7 warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
8
9 df = pd.read_excel('climate_finance_v3_data_2002_2023.xlsx')
10 print(f"Dataset: {df.shape[0]} obs, {df.shape[1]} vars")
```

2 Resilience Index V3 (No Circularity)

```
1 # Normalise components
2 df['life_expectancy_norm'] = (df['life_expectancy'] - df['life_expectancy'].min()) / (
3     df['life_expectancy'].max() - df['life_expectancy'].min())
4 df['gfcf_gdp_norm'] = (df['gfcf_gdp'] - df['gfcf_gdp'].min()) / (
5     df['gfcf_gdp'].max() - df['gfcf_gdp'].min())
6
7 # Resilience Index V3 - EXCLUDES fiscal-governance capacity
8 df['resilience_index_v3'] = (df['electricity_access'] * 0.35 +
9     df['renewable_energy'] * 0.25 +
10     df['life_expectancy_norm'] * 100 * 0.25 +
11     df['gfcf_gdp_norm'] * 100 * 0.15)
12 df['resilience_index_v3'] = ((df['resilience_index_v3'] - df['resilience_index_v3'].min()) /
13     (df['resilience_index_v3'].max() - df['resilience_index_v3'].min())) * 100
14
15 # Energy transition index
16 df['energy_transition_index_v3'] = (df['electricity_access'] * 0.5 +
17     df['renewable_energy'] * 0.3 +
18     df['gfcf_gdp_norm'] * 100 * 0.2)
```

3 Interaction Terms and Lags

```
1 df['cf_x_fiscal_gov'] = df['climate_finance_gdp'] * df['fiscal_gov_capacity_index']
2 df['shock_x_cf'] = df['climate_shock_exposure'] * df['climate_finance_gdp']
3 df = df.sort_values(['country', 'year'])
4 df['l1_climate_finance_gdp'] = df.groupby('country')['climate_finance_gdp'].shift(1)
5 df['spatial_lag_cf'] = df.groupby(['year', 'region'])['climate_finance_gdp'].transform(
6     lambda x: (x.sum() - x) / (len(x) - 1) if len(x) > 1 else x)
7 df['ln_gdp_pc'] = np.log(df['gdp_pc'])
8 df['ln_population'] = np.log(df['population'])
9 df['ln_inflation'] = np.log(1 + df['inflation'])
```

4 Main Analysis (Tables 2 and 3)

```
1 controls = ['ln_gdp_pc', 'ln_population', 'trade_openness',
2            'urbanization', 'ln_inflation', 'debt_gdp']
3 df_main = df.dropna(subset=['sdg_index', 'climate_finance_gdp',
4                            'fiscal_gov_capacity_index', 'cf_x_fiscal_gov'] + controls)
5
6 # Pooled OLS
7 X = sm.add_constant(df_main[['climate_finance_gdp', 'fiscal_gov_capacity_index',
8                              'cf_x_fiscal_gov'] + controls])
9 m = sm.OLS(df_main['sdg_index'], X).fit(cov_type='HC1')
10 print(f"OLS: CF={m.params['climate_finance_gdp']:.4f}***, "
11       f"CFxFGC={m.params['cf_x_fiscal_gov']:.4f}***")
12
13 # Entity FE
14 df_fe = df_main.set_index(['country', 'year'])
15 exog = sm.add_constant(df_fe[['climate_finance_gdp', 'fiscal_gov_capacity_index',
16                               'cf_x_fiscal_gov'] + controls])
17 fe = PanelOLS(df_fe['sdg_index'], exog, entity_effects=True,
18               drop_absorbed=True).fit(cov_type='clustered', cluster_entity=True)
19 print(f"FE: CF={fe.params['climate_finance_gdp']:.4f}***, "
20       f"CFxFGC={fe.params['cf_x_fiscal_gov']:.4f}**")
21
22 # IV/2SLS
23 iv_data = df_main.dropna(subset=['l1_climate_finance_gdp', 'spatial_lag_cf'])
24 X_s1 = sm.add_constant(iv_data[['l1_climate_finance_gdp', 'spatial_lag_cf',
25                                  'fiscal_gov_capacity_index'] + controls])
26 s1 = sm.OLS(iv_data['climate_finance_gdp'], X_s1).fit()
27 cf_hat = s1.fittedvalues
28 X_s2 = np.column_stack([np.ones(len(cf_hat)), cf_hat,
29                          iv_data['fiscal_gov_capacity_index'].values,
30                          cf_hat * iv_data['fiscal_gov_capacity_index'].values])
31 for c in controls:
32     X_s2 = np.column_stack([X_s2, iv_data[c].values])
33 s2 = sm.OLS(iv_data['sdg_index'].values, X_s2).fit(cov_type='HC1')
34 f_stat = (s1.rsquared / 2) / ((1 - s1.rsquared) / (s1.nobs - 8))
35 print(f"IV: CF={s2.params[1]:.4f}***, First-stage F={f_stat:.2f}")
```

5 Mechanisms and Alternative Outcomes (Table 5)

```
1 # Mechanisms
2 mechanisms = {'Public Investment': 'gfcf_gdp',
3              'Electricity Access': 'electricity_access',
4              'Human Capital': 'human_capital_index'}
5 for name, var in mechanisms.items():
6     temp = df_main.dropna(subset=[var])
7     X_m = sm.add_constant(temp[['climate_finance_gdp',
8                                 'fiscal_gov_capacity_index', 'cf_x_fiscal_gov'] + controls])
9     mech = sm.OLS(temp[var], X_m).fit(cov_type='HC1')
10    print(f"{name}: CFxFGC={mech.params['cf_x_fiscal_gov']:.4f}")
11
12 # Alternative outcomes (V3 resilience - no circularity)
13 outcomes = {'Resilience V3': 'resilience_index_v3',
14             'Energy Transition': 'energy_transition_index_v3'}
15 for name, var in outcomes.items():
16     temp = df_main.dropna(subset=[var])
17     X_o = sm.add_constant(temp[['climate_finance_gdp',
18                                 'fiscal_gov_capacity_index', 'cf_x_fiscal_gov'] + controls])
19     o = sm.OLS(temp[var], X_o).fit(cov_type='HC1')
20    print(f"{name}: CFxFGC={o.params['cf_x_fiscal_gov']:.4f}")
```

Expected Key Results

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant. Resilience V3 excludes fiscal-governance capacity.

Table	Specification	CF	CF × FGC
Table 2	Pooled OLS	0.675***	0.030***
Table 3	Entity FE	1.313***	0.011**
Table 3	IV/2SLS	1.225***	0.014 (ns)
Table 5	Mechanism: Public Invest.	–	0.011***
Table 5	Mechanism: Electr. Access	–	0.018**
Table 5	Mechanism: Human Capital	–	0.022***
Table 5	Resilience Index V3	-1.512***	0.059***
Table 5	Energy Transition	-0.739***	0.025***